

THE MEANING OF CAUSATION IN LINGUOCOGNITIVE ASPECT

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ABSTRACT

In this article the author analyzed the background of causation in linguocognitive aspect. The author compared causative verbs in two languages by translating sentences from English to Uzbek.

KEYWORDS

Causation, linguistics, grammar, semantics

1. INTRODUCTION

Causation is very important from social and communicative pragmatic point of view and is closely connected with the rapid development of cognitive linguistics. The modern linguistics is characterized by investigating the real task of the language in linguocognitive aspect. This process is focused on putting the cognitive semantics into first place. Investigating the view of the world from the cognitive point of view is taken place in every field of language layer, it is because is given opportunity to learn the essence of the language in every aspect and realizing the main role of the language. Moreover, the basic task of contemporary linguistics, mainly, cognitive linguistics is to investigate the role of human factor in language and realization of language facts.

Pinker said that: “The causative verb is a common structure in English. It shows that somebody or something is indirectly responsible for an action. The subject doesn’t perform the action itself, but causes someone or something else to do it instead”.

Causative verb has been studied by linguists since the 60s of the XX century and is considered mainly within the framework of morphological, lexical causatives, analytic causative, or causative constructions that do not always the verb has causative semantics. Causative constructions, which include a causative the meaning of the verb are studied in linguistics along with other relevant questions of semantic syntax. Causative verbs are studied by many scientists. The theory of the causative and causative constructions was developed primarily such scientists as V. P. Nedyalkov, G. G. Silnitsky, A. A. Kholodovich, V. S. Khrakovsky, B. Comrie, M. Shibatani, L. Talmy.

Particular problems associated with CC, were also considered in the works of V.D.Kaliushchenko, O. N. Seliverstova, Yu. S. Stepanova, B. Abbot, A. Alsina, W. Croft, M. Haspelmath, B. Levin, R. H. T. Malka, T. Sanders, E. Sweetser, N. Sumbatova, D. Wunderlich and others.

2. METHODOLOGY

The nature of modern research in the field of cognitive linguistics indicates development of the methodological basis and terminological apparatus theory of causation.

Causative constructions are studied within the framework of different paradigms and approaches: M. Lemmens describes causative constructions in English, integrating achievements cognitive grammar, systemic functional grammar and relational grammar.

R. King formulates the following semantic criterion of causation: if the proposition expressed in the sentence entails the proposition that the object expressed by the direct object of the transitive verb is subject to state change, then such a construction is considered causative. He considers, that the interpretation of causative constructions in terms of spatial metaphor has advantages over traditional approaches because creates a common framework for explaining what was previously considered incompatible.

The concept of “causation” in the physical world means a continuous connection cause and effect. Any conceptually limited part, or “event” perceived as connected with the outside world external or internal causal relationships.

Causativity (from Latin causa - reason) or causality is defined as a semantic category that indicates on events or phenomena that give rise to other events or phenomena: eng. You make me feel sorry.

According to A.N. Prikhodko, causality as one of the basic ontological entities finds its embodiment in the language as a functional-semantic category causality, which reflects the relations of dependence, conditionality, logical correspondence and consistency of the phenomena of objective reality.

The category of causation, expressing the relationship of cause - effect, is interpreted as a lexical parameter indicating events or phenomena, generating other events or phenomena, verbal category, functional-semantic, lexico-grammatical category, expressing a wide range of intra-phrasal relations that can be in generally characterized as a cause-effect relationship, as universal typological category, characterized by a wide range of means of expression in languages with different structures.

Causativity was also studied within the framework of the linguo-cognitive approach. So, for example, causal relationships are seen as a concept REASON. P.Salo believes that causation is rather part of the “logical syntax” of a single sentence, and not part of any of its lexical elements.

3. RESULTS

There are different approaches to interpreting types of causation. Linguistic literature distinguishes the following types of causative relations:

Logical relation

Relation “means – goal” (a means - purpose relation)

The relationship “means – result” (a means - result relation)

The relation “cause – result” (a reason – result relation).

Modern linguistic science is characterized interdisciplinary and focuses primarily on anthropocentric approach in the process of linguistic analysis. Linguistic anthropocentrism is the

dominant principle modern studies of language units and categories, “presence of a person makes itself felt throughout the entire space of language”. In this context, modern linguistic studies, including typological and comparative, the complex approach to the consideration of multi-level units and categories. While in focus attention is paid to their various aspects. In this research, this approach integrates the conceptual apparatus and methods typological and comparative linguistics, functional semantic, cognitive linguistics, constructional grammar.

The focus of the study is causative connective verbs. In this regard, one of the tasks was to determine the corpus of causative verbs in English verbs expressing the relation of causation, which is a synonym causal relationship. So the causative verb expresses the value of causation and the value of the state being caused.

In the article "Morphological causative in the Georgian language" I. O. Getsadze, V. P. Nedyalkov and A. A. Kholodovich note that the term “causative verb” is used in two meanings: semantic and formal. Corpus of causatives verbs in English includes both “formal” causative verbs, so are verbs, which can express causation relations only in certain contexts.

The lexicographic part of the sample in English was 135 verbs, including: **let, make, cause, get, have, produce, bring about, effect, lead to, induce, result in, engender, effectuate, occasion, stir, generate, provoke, touch off, hatch, breed, spawn**, etc.

The most wide-ranging verbs with a causative meaning in English are the verbs **let, make, cause, get, have**. These verbs are often erroneously considered and more or less interchangeable.

Synonyms of the verb to let in the causative meaning are 14 verbs, obtained by continuous sampling from Roget's II Electronic Thesaurus dictionary:

- 1) to afford an opportunity for- imkoniyatga ega bo'lish allow, permit, admit;
- 2) to engage in the temporary use of (something) for a fee- to'lov evaziga (bir narsadan) vaqtincha foydalanish bilan shug'ullanish uchun: hire, rent, lease, charter;
- 3) to give one's consent to- rozilik bermoq: allow, permit, authorize, sanction, consent;
- 4) to neither forbid nor prevent- na ta'qiqlash, na oldini olish: have, leave, allow, suffer, tolerate

Synonyms of the verb **to make** in the causative sense are 58 verbs, obtained by the method of continuous sampling from the Roget's II Electronic dictionary Thesaurus, for example:

- 1) **to be the cause of** -sabab bo'lmoq: produce, bring about, effect, lead to, induce, result in, engender, occasion, effectuate;
- 2) **to cause (a person or thing) to act or move in spite of resistance** -shaxsni yoki narsani qarshilik ko'rsatishga yoki harakat qilishga majburlash: force, compel, oblige, coerce, constraint, pressure;
- 3) **to cause to be by official action**-rasmiy harakat bilan bo'lishiga sabab bo'lmoq: establish, constitute, enact, legislate;
- 4) to cause to come into existence-vujudga kelishiga sabab bo'lmoq: generate, originate, engender, hatch, father, sire, parent, procreate, spawn.

Synonyms of the verb to get in the causative sense are 47 verbs, for example:

- 1) to acquire as a result of one's behavior or effort-x ulq-atvori yoki harakatlari natijasida egallash - win, gain, earn, deserve, merit;

- 2) to be the biological father of- biologik otasi bo'lish: -beget, breed, father, sire, procreate;
- 3) to come into possession of- egalik qilmoq: - obtain, win, come by, gain, acquire, land, secure, pick up, procure;
- 4) to come to be- bo'lmoq: become, turn, grow, wax;
- 5) to gain knowledge or mastery of by study- o'qish orqali bilim olish yoki o'zlashtirish: learn, pick up, master;
- 6) to gain possession of, especially after a struggle or chase- egalik qilish, ayniqsa qiyinchilik bilan erishilgandan keyin: take, catch, capture, secure, net;

The verb have in a causative meaning is used in two types of syntactic constructions. I. The construction have + object + infinitive / -ing form The construction “have + object + infinitive” has the meaning “cause somebody to do something”

1. “I’m ready to see Mr Smith. Have him come in, please”– Men janob Smitni ko'rishga tayyorman. Iltimos, uni ichkariga kiriting.
2. “We cannot have them back” – Biz ularni qaytarib ololmaymiz.
3. “I’ll have Hudson show you to your room” –Men Gudsondan sizni xonangizni ko'rsatishini so'rayman.

The causative “have + object + -ing form” has the meaning “cause somebody to be doing something”, that is, just as in the “have + object + infinitive” construction, “kimnidir biror narsa qilishga majburlash”, but with an emphasis on long-term action (be doing).

4. “This is a fabulously witty book which had me laughing out loud on multiple occasions” - Bu juda aqlli kitob bo'lib, u meni bir necha bor baland ovozda kuldirdi.
5. “He believed in them. He had them believing in themselves” - U ularga ishondi. U ularni o'zlariga ishontirdi
6. “She had me doing all kinds of jobs for her” – U meni o'zi uchun har xil ishlarni qilishga majbur qildi.

Have + object + past participle.

This causative construction has the meaning «cause something to be done by somebody else» biror narsaning boshqa birov tomonidan qilinishiga sabab bo'lmoq.

The essence of the causative with the past participle is that the action is performed not by the agent, but by another person at the request / request of the agent. Thus, this construction retains the dominance of the nuclear component «causative influence by the desire / will of the agent (causator) on the patient (causable)».

7. “While the Abbey Theatre prepares to shut for the summer to have its roof repaired, the Olympia on Dublin’s Dame Street has sprung a leak” – Abbey teatri yozda tomini ta'mirlash uchun yopilishga tayyorgarlik ko'rayotgan bir paytda, Dublinning Dame ko'chasidagi Olimpiada suv oqishi sodir bo'ldi.
8. “If you don’t get out of my house I’ll have you arrested” – Agar uyimdan chiqmasang, seni politsiyaga topshiraman.
9. “We’d only just had a new engine put in” –Biz hozirgina yangi dvigatel o'rnatdik.

It is important to make a clear distinction between the causative construction “have + object + past participle” and the verb have with a passive meaning “if you have something stolen, broken etc, someone steals, breaks etc something that belongs to you”. In the latter case, have serves to denote an action that occurs against the will / will of the subject:

10. “Rebekah Brooks, the former chief executive of News International, had her phone hacked by News of the World twice a week ...” - News International kompaniyasining sobiq bosh direktori Rebeka Bruksning telefoni haftada ikki marta News of the World tomonidan buzilgan.
11. “She had all her jewelery stolen”– Uning barcha taqinchoqlari o'g'irlangan.

The context suggests which aspect of the causative influence takes place in a given situation. One thing remains unchanged: the causative effect of the desire / will of the agent (causator) on the patient (causable) is the nuclear component in the semantics of the causative verb have.

1. "I'm ready to see Mr Smith. Have him come in, please" – Men janob Smitni ko'rishga tayyorman. Iltimos, uni ichkariga kiriting.
2. "We cannot have them back" – Biz ularni qaytarib ololmaymiz.
3. "I'll have Hudson show you to your room" –Men Gudsondan sizni xonangizni ko'rsatishini so'rayman.

4. DISCUSSION

Causative constructions seem to have a special status in linguistics and, presumably, in language too. The notion of cause and effect, which lies at their centre, is believed to be fundamental in the whole of human cognition. Lakoff and Johnson, for example, state that it is a "basic human concept" ((Lakoff & Johnson, 1980) cited by Gilquin (2010, p. 1)).

Active causative structure is used when someone causes something to happen or when a person causes another one to take an action. Consider:

Railway station security **had** everyone **show** their tickets. Temir yo'l vokzalining qo'riqlash xizmati barchani chiptalarini ko'rsatishini talab qildi.

The tutor **made** his students **do** an oral interpretation. O'qituvchi o'z shogirdlarini og'zaki talqin qilishga majbur qildi

It's also important to note that some causative verbs require the bare infinitive, namely when using have, let, and make. **Other common causative actions require the to-infinitive**, such as: convince, allow, encourage, permit, employ, help, get, require, motivate, hire, assist, command, force, order, remind, urge and force.

The magazine **encouraged** all readers **to** submit suggestions for future issues.

Jurnal barcha o'quvchilarni kelgusi sonlar uchun takliflar berishga undadi

Passive structure is used to talk about having something done by another person/thing. Consider the following example:

The president had his speech written by a very talented group of writers. Prezident nutqi juda iste'dodli yozuvchilar guruhi tomonidan yozilgan.

In this case, the person (The president) arranged for something(writing a speech).

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